

Valorization of dairy wastewater: High-yield biomass and hydrogen production using an alga-bacterium consortium

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ABSTRACT

The microalgae *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* and the bacterium *Microbacterium forte* formed a successful consortium when cultivated in both simulated and raw Dairy Wastewater (DWW) with high organic loads (Chemical Oxygen Demand of 7346–12,000 mg·L⁻¹). Substantial biomass yield (up to 11.27 g·L⁻¹ 1.25 g·L⁻¹·d⁻¹) and biohydrogen (up to 185.8 mL·L⁻¹) were obtained using simulated DWW. Moreover, the use of cocultures reduced CO₂ emissions (71–89 %) compared to sole bacterial cultures. Supplementation with trace elements was sufficient to grow the consortium in DWW without requiring other major nutrient sources. *Chlamydomonas* and *M. forte* established a mutualistic relationship that benefited the growth of both microorganisms. The proteolytic activity of *M. forte* and the subsequent release of ammonium, along with the excretion of acetic acid by the bacterium, represent the core of this mutualistic relationship. This study presents potential solutions for the bioremediation and valorization of DWW with high organic loads, where the use of pre-treatment methods is not feasible on an industrial scale.

1. Introduction

The dairy industry plays a significant role in the global food sector, but it is also considered one of the most polluting industries in many countries (Stasinakis et al., 2022). On average, processing one liter of milk generates between 1 and 3 liters of dairy wastewater (DWW), which contains high levels of organic matter. The Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) of DWW often exceeds 2000 mg·L⁻¹ and can reach up to 68,000 mg·L⁻¹ (Boguniewicz-Zablocka et al., 2019; Kumar et al., 2023; Stasinakis et al., 2022). Consequently, the dairy industry is required to treat DWW to mitigate ecological risks, particularly eutrophication of water bodies. Moreover, within the industrial food sector, dairy industries are among the largest consumers of water, estimated at 1–10 m³ of water per m³ of processed milk (Stasinakis et al., 2022). Most DWW originates from milk spillage and Clean-In-Place (CIP) operations (Stasinakis et al., 2022), which are standardized cleaning routines used to rinse and wash processing equipment after each production cycle. These operations alone account for 32–75 % of total water consumption (Buabeng-Baidoo et al., 2017; Stasinakis et al., 2022). The resulting DWWs (commonly referred to as white waters or rinse waters) are mostly composed of diluted dairy products (e.g. milk, whey) mixed with

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varying amounts of sanitizing agents. Due to the variability of CIP operations and dairy products, the composition of DWW can fluctuate greatly, even on a daily basis. DWW treatment (DWWT) typically combines mechanical, physico-chemical and biological processes. Among these, biological processes (primarily bacterial) are generally preferred for their lower cost, versatility and efficiency in degrading organic pollutants (Slavov, 2017; Sravan et al., 2024). Biological process often combine aerobic and anaerobic systems. Aerobic systems are very effective in reducing organic load but require high O₂ inputs, which implies higher energy demand. Anaerobic systems are more energy-efficient but generally slower than aerobic systems. Moreover, in some cases, anaerobic treatments are associated with significant releases of greenhouse gases such as CH₄, CO₂ and N₂O (Chandra et al., 2018; Pell and Wörman, 2008; Ranieri et al., 2023; Slavov, 2017; Sravan et al., 2024).

In response to growing environmental concerns, there is increasing pressure on the dairy sector to adopt cleaner, more sustainable practices, especially regarding energy and water use (Buabeng-Baidoo et al., 2017; Sravan et al., 2024; Stasinakis et al., 2022). In this context, the principles of circular economy and bioeconomy are gaining traction, offering new avenues for wastewater valorization. One particularly promising strategy involves the use of algae and algae-bacteria systems, which can enhance pollutant removal, capture CO₂, reduce O₂ inputs, and produce valuable algal biomass (e.g. biofertilizers, feeds, biofuel, bioplastics, or proteins), as well as the direct production of other valuable bioproducts such as methane or biohydrogen (bioH₂) (Anand et al., 2023; Aydin et al., 2021; Jiang et al., 2021; Kishor et al., 2024; Li et al., 2023; Mathew et al., 2022; Mohsenpour et al., 2021; Mona et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2022).

Several studies have shown that microalgae can grow in DWW and contribute to its remediation while producing biomass, mostly for lipid extraction (reviewed by Gupta et al. 2019). However, very few studies have addressed how the native bacterial populations present in DWW affect algal growth (Roy et al., 2023) or how algae perform in consortia with other microorganisms (Kumar et al., 2023). Roy et al. (2023) observed that *Chlorella vulgaris* cocultured with activated sludge outperformed monocultures, while Kumar et al. (2023) reported that coculturing *Scenedesmus abundans* with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* in raw DWW enhanced biomass production. Nonetheless, there is a notable lack of studies about the algal-bacteria interactions that occur in DWW environments. Understanding these interactions could be crucial for designing effective algal-based treatment systems.

A recent study has shown that a consortium of *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* and *Microbacterium forte* can form a mutualistic relationship in synthetic media containing peptides and sugars (including lactose), leading to high levels of biomass and hydrogen production (Fakhimi et al., 2024).

Building on that work, the present study explores the growth, bioremediation potential, and hydrogen production capacity of the *Chlamydomonas-M. forte* consortium cultivated in both simulated and raw DWW with high organic loads. The study also investigates the interactions between the two organisms to inform the design of future algae-bacteria systems for sustainable wastewater treatment and valorization.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Algal and bacterial strains and preculturing conditions

The *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* CC-1690 (21 gr, mt⁺) and 704 (cw15, arg7⁺, Nia1:ArS, mt⁺) (Loppes et al., 1999) strains were used. Strain 704 was used exclusively for H₂ production experiments, whereas CC-1690 was used for all other assays. The CC-1690 strain is available from the Chlamydomonas Resource Centre repository, while the 704 strain is maintained in our laboratory collection. The microalgal precultures were grown photomixotrophically in Tris Acetate Phosphate (TAP) medium (Harris, 2009) at 24°C, under continuous Photosynthetic Photon Flux Density (PPFD) of 60–90 μmol photon · m⁻² · s⁻¹ provided by LED panels, and continuous agitation (140 rpm) for 3–4 days until mid-logarithmic phase. Cells were then harvested by centrifugation (3000 x g for 5 min) and washed twice with Minimal Mineral (MM) medium (Harris, 2009) prior to their use as inocula for cocultures. The bacterium *Microbacterium forte* (Fakhimi et al., 2024) was precultured in Luria Broth (LB) medium at 28 °C for 18–24 h under agitation (140 rpm) until reaching and OD₆₀₀ of 0.8–1. Bacterial cells were then collected by centrifugation (8000 x g for 5 min) and washed twice with fresh MM medium prior to their use as inocula for cocultures.

M. forte was previously isolated in our laboratory facilities and deposited in the Colección Española de Cultivos Tipo (CECT) under accession number CECT30765.

2.2. Media and coculturing conditions of *Chlamydomonas* and *M. forte*

The compositions (per liter) of the different media used for the cocultures are as follows: MMn, MM without NH₄Cl and with 0.4 g KNO₃; TAPn, TAP without NH₄Cl and with 0.4 g KNO₃; MLT, MM with 3.4 g lactose and 2.5 g tryptone; WM, commercial ultra-pasteurized Whole milk (COVAP Ltd.); WM-MM, whole milk diluted with MM; WM-H₂O, whole milk diluted with distilled H₂O; sDWW, WM-H₂O (1:10) supplemented with trace elements; Trace elements, 0.05 g EDTA, 5.1 mg MnCl₂·4H₂O, 22 mg ZnCl₂, 11 mg H₃BO₃, 1.6 mg CoCl₂·6 H₂O, 1.6 mg CuCl₂·2 H₂O, 0.214 mg Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O and 5 mg FeSO₄; raw DWW, white waters obtained from COVAP Ltd. (Pozoblanco, Spain). All media were autoclaved, except for WM and raw DWW; WM was maintained under sterile conditions. When needed, lactose was filter-sterilized before being added to the corresponding autoclaved media.

Initial COD values for sDWW and raw DWW were of 12,077 mg·L⁻¹ and 7346 mg·L⁻¹, respectively. Initial pH values were 7.0 (sDWW) and 6.5 (raw DWW). Other initial physiochemical parameters for sDWW were 0.354 % fats, 2.12 mg·mL⁻¹ proteins, 2.61 mM ammonium, 13 mM lactose, and 0.874 % Solid-Not-Fat (SNF).

Algal-bacterial cocultures were prepared using cells from precultures and adjusted to an initial chlorophyll concentration of

5 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ for growth experiments or 10 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ for H_2 production experiments, and an initial OD_{600} of 0.02 for the bacterium. When needed, algal and bacterial monocultures were included as controls. All cultures were cultivated in batch mode.

For growth experiments, algae and bacteria were cocultivated using 125 or 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks, each containing 50 or 100 mL of the corresponding medium, respectively. All cultures were incubated at 24 °C under continuous top illumination (80 PPFD) and agitation (140 rpm), unless otherwise indicated. In some experiments, illumination was provided from below (80 PPFD), and cultures were maintained without agitation.

For H_2 production experiments, cocultures (100 mL) were placed in 155 mL bioreactors sealed with screw caps fitted with butyl septa (WHEATON, cat. No. 240680). Cultures were incubated at 24 °C with continuous agitation (200 rpm) and illumination of 50–500 PPFD using a growth chamber equipped with LED panels (AlgaeTron AG 230, Photon System Instruments). Bioreactors were opened under sterile conditions every 24 h (aeration) to release the H_2 partial pressure and replace the gas composition in the headspace with atmospheric air (Jurado-Oller et al., 2015). Daily H_2 production and O_2 levels in the headspace were measured before the aeration of the bioreactors.

For CO_2 measurements, cultures (350 mL) were placed in 1 L bottles (DURAN™) sealed with screw caps (GL 45 with 2 connectors) (DWK Life Sciences, Mainz, Germany), and incubated at 24 °C either under continuous top illumination (80 PPFD) and agitation (140 rpm) or under bottom illumination (80 PPFD) and without agitation.

2.3. Measurement of alga and bacteria growth

Total chlorophyll was used as an indirect estimation of algal growth. Pigments were extracted with 96 % ethanol and determined spectrophotometrically (DU 800, Beckman Coulter) according to the equation of Wintermans and De Mots (1965): Total chlorophyll ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) = $\text{Abs}_{665} \times 6,01 + \text{Abs}_{649} \times 20,04$. Bacterial growth in monocultures was estimated spectrophotometrically in terms of OD_{600} evolution. In cocultures, bacterial growth was estimated using a customized Selective Centrifugal Sedimentation (SCS) approach (Fakhimi et al., 2024; Torres et al., 2022). This approach optimizes centrifugation conditions to sediment most algal cells while leaving bacterial cells in suspension. Thus, OD_{600} measurements of the supernatant after centrifugation offer an estimation of the bacterial growth in the cocultures. Briefly, the cocultures were centrifuged at 13,000 rpm and the pellets were resuspended in 1 mL of MM medium. Then the samples were centrifuged at 200 x g for 1 min, (SCS parameters previously determined for *Chlamydomonas* and *M. forte*) (Torres et al., 2022) and the OD_{600} of the supernatants were measured ($^{\text{SCS}}\text{OD}_{600}$).

Dry-weight biomass was determined by centrifuging 40–50 mL of cultures (8,000 x g for 5 min.) and weighing the resulting pellets. The pellets were dried at 65 °C for 24 h before weighing. The pH was measured using a LAQUAtwin-pH-33 compact pH meter (Horiba Scientific).

2.4. Metabolites analysis

Ammonium (NH_4^+) levels in culture supernatants were quantified using Nessler's reagents (MERCK 109011 and 109012). Equal volumes of fresh Nessler's reagents and cell-free supernatants (1:10 dilutions) were mixed and incubated for 5 min. Absorbance at 415 nm was measured using a microplate reader (iMark, Bio-Rad). Calibration curves for each set of samples were generated using increasing NH_4Cl concentrations. Protein concentration in the cell-free supernatants was estimated using the Bradford assay (Bio-Rad Laboratories, Richmond, CA). Calibration curves were constructed using a standard range of bovine serum albumin.

Lactose, acetic acid, and lactic acid concentrations were determined by HPLC (Agilent series 1200, Agilent Technologies) equipped with an ion-exchange column (Agilent Hi-Plex H, 300 x 7.7 mm, 6 μm I. D.) and using isocratic elution with 5 mM H_2SO_4 at 50 °C. Free-cell supernatants were filtered (0.2 μm) and injected (20 μL) into the HPLC at a flow rate of 0.6 $\text{mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$. Samples were diluted 10-fold before filtration when necessary. Peaks were detected using a Refractive Index Detector (RID). Quantification was based on calibration curves prepared with standard solutions of the corresponding compounds.

Carbon dioxide (CO_2) emissions were quantified using a Cavity Ring-Down Spectroscopy (CRDS) analyzer (PICARRO G2508). Culture bottles (1 L) were connected to the CRDS system through two teflon tubes (3 m in length each) to allow gas recirculation (0.3 $\text{L} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$). To prevent contamination, return gas was filtered through a 0.22 μm PVDF membrane (Dualect™-Plus, Merck).

Gas chromatograph (GC) (Agilent 7820 A, Agilent Technologies) was used to measure H_2 and O_2 . Gas samples from the headspaces (250 μL) were collected using a 1 mL Hamilton's SampleLock™ syringe and manually injected into the GC. H_2 and O_2 were separated using a packed column (60/80 Molecular Sieve 5 A, Ref. 13,133-U, Supelco) at 75 °C and detected using a Thermal Conductivity Detector (TCD). Argon was used as the carrier gas.

Chemical oxygen demand (COD) was determined using the Spectroquant® COD Cell Test commercial kit (Merck) following the manufacturer's protocol. Measurements were performed using a Spectroquant® Colorimeter Move100 (Merck).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Stimulation of *Chlamydomonas* growth by *Microbacterium forte* in a synthetic tryptone–lactose medium (MLT)

A synthetic medium (MTL) was formulated to assess the ability of the *Chlamydomonas*-*M. forte* consortium to grow on lactose (3.4 g $\cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) and tryptone (2.5 g $\cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) incubated under 80 PPFD. *Chlamydomonas* monocultures incubated in MLT, standard autotrophic (MMn), and mixotrophic (TAPn) media, were employed as controls. *Chlamydomonas* grown in MLT medium reached chlorophyll levels over four times higher in cocultures (67.4 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) than in monocultures (15.5 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) (Supplemental Fig. S1). Algal growth in the

consortium was likely mixotrophic, increasing steadily to $67.4 \mu\text{g chlorophyll} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$ over the 7-day incubation. Mixotrophic growth would indicate the presence of acetic acid in the culture medium (the only assimilable organic carbon source for *Chlamydomonas*) originating from the metabolism of lactose by *M. forte*. In contrast, the growth of the algal monocultures was primarily autotrophic, confirming that *Chlamydomonas* cannot use lactose as a carbon source. Note that algal monocultures grown in the standard mixotrophic TAPn medium (containing acetic acid and nitrate as the sole organic carbon and nitrogen sources, respectively), reached peak chlorophyll levels ($37.2 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$) at day 3, followed by a decline. This chlorophyll decline was likely caused by a rise in pH (11.2 at day 3), a common effect in media where nitrate is the sole nitrogen source (Scherholz and Curtis, 2013).

3.2. Evaluation of *Chlamydomonas* growth in consortium with *Microbacterium forte* in simulated DWW (sDWW)

White waters (also known as rinse waters) are the most abundant DWW. They are mostly composed of diluted milk and dairy products resulting from leaks and CIP operations. Nevertheless, information on the exact composition of these DWWs is scarce (Slavov, 2017). Moreover, due to the uneven CIP operations and leaks, their composition can be highly variable within a specific dairy industry, even on an hourly basis, resulting in large variations (e.g., COD concentrations can range from 300 to 68000 $\text{mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) (Brião et al., 2019; Kumar et al., 2023). Hence, standardizing the composition of DWW and ensuring reproducibility of results represents a significant challenge.

To avoid variations in the composition of DWW and to allow for better experimental reproducibility, different dilutions of commercial Whole Milk (WM) were used to mimic white waters. In addition to providing greater stability in nutrient composition, the use of pasteurized WM eliminates the need for pretreatment to remove the bacterial communities naturally present in DWW (Beevi and Sukumaran, 2014; Hena et al., 2015; Huo et al., 2012; Lu et al., 2016; Qin et al., 2014). Also, the absence of naturally occurring

Fig. 1. Chlorophyll concentrations of *Chlamydomonas* in consortium with *M. forte* in sDWW: effect of dilutions and nutrient supplementation. A) *Chlamydomonas*-*M. forte* consortium cultivated in undiluted whole milk (WM) and in 1:2, 1:5 and 1:10 dilutions. Dilutions were performed with MM medium (WM-MM). Cocultures in TAP and MM media were included as controls. B) Actual photographs of the consortium cultures incubated in WM and WM-MM after 7 days. C) *Chlamydomonas*-*M. forte* cocultures cultivated in 1:10 WM dilutions with water (WM-H₂O (1:10)) and supplemented by single and pairwise combinations of nutrients: NH₄Cl (N), MgSO₄·7 H₂O (S), phosphate buffer (P) or Trace elements (T). The final concentrations for all nutrients were as in MM medium. 1:10 WM-MM was included as control. Conditions including trace elements are framed. D) Actual photographs of cocultures incubated in panel C. For all experiments, cells were cultivated under continuous top illumination (80 PPFD) and agitation. Data represent the means of at least three biological replicates, and Standard Error of the Mean (SEM) values are indicated. SEM bars may not be visible in the current graphic scales.

bacteria simplifies the process of monitoring algal growth and the potential interactions with co-inoculated bacteria.

3.2.1. Effect of dilutions and nutrient supplementation

The capacity of *Chlamydomonas-M. forte* cocultures to grow on WM diluted with the autotrophic MM medium (WM-MM) was evaluated at 80 PPFD (Figs. 1A and 1B). Inoculation of the consortium in milk diluted 5 or 10 times (COD 24,000 and 12,077 mg·L⁻¹, respectively) resulted in a significant and sustained increase in chlorophyll content (up to 61.4 µg · mL⁻¹ after 7 days in the 1:10 dilution). As occurred with the MLT medium (Supplemental Fig. S1), the algal growth in the 1:5 and 1:10 dilutions was likely mixotrophic.

Undiluted milk or 1:2 dilutions (COD of 120,000 and 60,000 mg·L⁻¹, respectively) resulted in poor algal growth in the consortium. Osmotic stress (e.g. high lactose concentration) or/and poor light penetrance (milk opacity) may explain this. *Chlamydomonas* monocultures barely grew in the 1:10 milk dilution (13.1 µg chlorophyll · mL⁻¹ after 7 days), confirming that the alga is unable to grow mixotrophically in WM-MM on its own.

Compared to cocultures grown in TAP medium, cocultures cultivated in WM-MM exhibited delayed algae growth, most likely due

Table 1

Comparison of selected publications using raw DWW for algal cultivation. The selection focuses primarily on studies employing white waters as DWW, excluding those based on manure or secondary effluents from DWW treatment plants. N.I.: Not indicated; ¹, Sterilization method is not indicated; ², assuming biomass was collected after 15 days; ³, As Total Volatile Suspend Solids (TVSS) or Total Suspended Solid (TSS).

Alga	Type of DWW, pre-treatments and growth conditions	Initial COD (mg·L ⁻¹)	Final COD (mg·L ⁻¹)	Biomass (g·L ⁻¹ /g·L ⁻¹ ·d ⁻¹)	Ref.
<i>Chlamydomonas reinhardtii</i> + <i>Microbacterium forte</i>	Simulated DWW (1:10 milk), trace element supplementation	12,077	5430	11.3 / 1.25	This study
<i>Poteroiochromonas malhamensis</i>	BG-11 medium dissolved in DWW derived from a whey processing industry. CO ₂ (5 %) supplementation	10,300	2081	~11.6 / 0.89	Módenes et al. (2024)
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	Whey WW (mother liquor) mixed with slaughterhouse WW.	9550	8022	3.24 ³ / 0.54 ³	Lu et al. (2016)
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	Sterilization at 121°C and ammonium supplementation	6410	~1000	4.5 ³ /	Sánchez-Zurano et al. (2024)
<i>Chlamydomonas polyphyrenoides</i>	Artificial whey (milk + 5 % acetic acid). Air bubbling and supplementation with fertilizers	6000	1056	3.8 / 0.38	Kothari et al. (2013)
<i>Desmodesmus sp.</i>	Diluted DWW	5250	N.I.	4.92/0.35	Salah et al. (2023)
<i>Euglena gracilis</i> WZSL mutant	Diluted cheese whey supplemented with mineral medium	4464	397	3.2 / 0.64	Barsanti et al. (2021)
<i>Spirulina platensis</i>	Whey WW mixed with other WW streams. Culturing through dialysis system	3747	N.I.	~0.6/0.075	Zapata et al. (2021)
<i>Acutodesmus dimorphus</i>	Partially degreased DWW. Filtering to remove solids	2593	215	0.84 / 0.21	Chokshi et al. (2016)
<i>Scenedesmus abundans</i> + <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	DWW diluted with stormwater and filtering to remove suspended solids	2042	344	1.9 / 0.135	Kumar et al. (2023)
<i>Desmococcus olivaceus</i>	Initially, DWW diluted (20 %) with fertilizers, followed by full DWW replacement. Filtering to remove solids. Aeration	1960	336	1.44	Kanagam and Rajasekaran (2023)
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	DWW. Filtration and sterilization with sodium hypochlorite	1352	649	1.87 / 0.45	Qin et al. (2014)
<i>Scenedesmus sp.</i>	DWW after grit and settling process	989-1100	N.I.	~2.11 / 0.211	Hena et al. (2015)
<i>Chlorococcum sp. RAP13</i>	Sterilized ¹ DWW. Supplementation with glycerol	984	60	1.94/0.13 ²	Beevi and Sukumaran (2014)
<i>Scenedesmus SDEC13</i>	DWW. Filtering to remove suspended solids	886	233	1.64 / ~0.15	Ma et al. (2023)
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i> + bacterial sludge	Partially degreased DWW	800	96	1.52 / 0.19	Roy et al. (2023)
<i>Chlorella sp.</i>	Diluted DWW. Settled by gravity and filtered	648	118	~3/0.338	Lu et al. (2016)
<i>Tetraselmis suecica</i>	DWW. pH adjustment and salt supplementation	679	N.I.	0.61 / 0.08	Daneshvar et al. (2018)
<i>Scenedesmus quadricauda</i>	DWW. pH adjustment	654	N.I.	0.47 / 0.06	Daneshvar et al. (2018)
<i>Chlorella zofingiensis</i>	Diluted DWW. Sterilization at 121°C and acetic acid supplementation	119.5	N.I.	0.175	Huo et al. (2012)
<i>Chlorella pyrenoidosa</i>	Diluted DWW	N.I.	N.I.	6.8 / 0.45	Kothari et al. (2012)
<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	DWWTP effluents	356	69	1.23/0.17	Choi (2016)
<i>Chlorella sorokiniana</i>	Sterilized ¹ DWWTP effluents. Removal of colloidal particles. Two phase cultivation (photoautotrophic and heterotrophic)	1073		7.29	Hena et al. (2015)
<i>Arthrospira platensis</i>	Cattel farm WWTP effluents. Centrifugation and CO ₂ supplementation	131	2.11	5.35 / 0.52	Hena et al. (2018)
<i>Chlorella protothecoides</i>	Diluted chemically hydrolyzed whey. Dried and pH adjustment	1693	125	4.33/0.48	Patel et al. (2020)

to the initial low availability of acetic acid. Nevertheless, unlike TAP cocultures, algal growth in WM-MM was sustained over 7 days, leading to more than a twofold increase in chlorophyll accumulation (61.4 vs. $28.4 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$) (Fig. 1A).

Notably, no algal growth was observed when the consortium was cultured in 1:10 dilution of WM using distilled water as diluent (WM-H₂O), instead of MM medium (Fig. 1C). This suggests that certain essential nutrients supplied by MM are necessary to support the algal growth observed in WM-MM. To further investigate this, WM-H₂O medium was supplemented with individual essential nutrients (N, S, P, and trace elements) in both single and pairwise combinations (Figs. 1C and 1D). Only cultures supplemented with trace elements supported algal growth, with no significant differences among the different media combinations containing them (48 – $55 \mu\text{g}$ chlorophyll $\cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$). These results indicate that trace elements are the only essential nutrient absent in the WM that prevents *Chlamydomonas* growth in consortium with *M. forte*. Considering these results, the 1:10 WM-H₂O dilution supplemented with trace elements was used as simulated DWW (sDWW) to further assess *Chlamydomonas* growth in coculture with *M. forte*.

Interestingly, Lu et al. (2016) reported that micronutrients do not limit *C. vulgaris* growth in certain types DWW (mother liquor, salt whey and liquid whey), suggesting that not all DWW require trace elements supplementation. In the present study, the 1:10 WM-H₂O dilutions were prepared with distilled water, likely resulting in a marked deficiency of trace elements. In practical applications, the use of raw water sources or supplementation with small volumes of other wastewater may readily provide trace elements to support algal growth. In previous studies, supplementation of DWW with ammonium (Lu et al., 2016), glycerol (Beevi and Sukumaran, 2014), rich synthetic media (e.g. BG-11) (Módenes et al., 2024; Nayana et al., 2024; Salah et al., 2023), fertilizers (Kanagam and Rajasekaran, 2023; Sánchez-Zurano et al., 2024) or other types of wastewater (Barsanti et al., 2021; Lu et al., 2016) have been shown to be essential for achieving high microalgal growth in DWW (Table 1). The addition of these nutrients can be costly and/or increase the organic load of the DWW, thereby complicating the bioremediation process. In contrast, *Chlamydomonas* grew efficiently in consortium with *M. forte* in sDWW without supplementation of N, C, P, or S, and the addition of trace elements does not markedly augment the COD of DWW. A more detailed study of the trace element requirements could help identify the specific micronutrients essential for *Chlamydomonas* growth.

3.2.2. Effect of agitation

To evaluate which of the two main metabolic modes of *M. forte* (aerobic or anaerobic) better supports *Chlamydomonas* growth, experiments were conducted with agitation (aerobiosis) and without agitation (microaerobiosis), all incubated at 80 PPFD. Cocultures incubated in MLT and sDWW were compared (Table 2). Unexpectedly, the effect of agitation on algal growth differed between media: in MLT, the absence of agitation benefited chlorophyll accumulation (67.4 and $97.7 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$ for agitated and non-agitated cultures, respectively), whereas in sDWW, the opposite was observed (65.3 and $36.8 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$ for agitated and non-agitated cultures, respectively). A possible explanation could be that, unlike MLT, the opacity of the milk in sDWW would severely hinder light penetration under non-agitated conditions at 80 PPFD, as most algal cells settle at the bottom of the flasks, thereby impairing algal growth. In contrast, light penetration in the transparent MLT medium is comparable to that of water. To assess whether limited light penetration was impeding algal growth in non-agitated sDWW cultures, a novel experimental setup was employed in which flasks were illuminated from below at 80 PPFD (instead of from above) (Supplemental Fig. S2). Under this condition, chlorophyll accumulation

Table 2

Growth, biomass, and CO₂ emissions of *Chlamydomonas* and *M. forte* in consortium and as monocultures. *Chlamydomonas* and *M. forte* growths were measured as total chlorophyll and ^{SCS}OD₆₀₀, respectively. All values were obtained after 7 days of cultivation. Cocultures were incubated in sDWW with agitation (a) or without agitation (w/a), under continuous light (80 PPFD). Cultures labelled with B.I. indicate that illumination was provided from the bottom the flasks. ¹ CO₂ levels correspond to 350 mL cultures incubated in 1 L sealed bottles, which initial CO₂ levels were 543 ppm ±2. sDWW not inoculated was included as a control. Data corresponds to the means of at least three biological replicates with Standard Error of the Mean (SEM) values indicated in brackets. Dash (-): not analyzed.

	Algal growth ($\mu\text{g chl} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$)	Bacterial growth (^{SCS} OD ₆₀₀)	Dry Weight ($\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$)	CO ₂ levels ¹ (ppm)	COD ($\text{mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$)
Consortium (MLT, a)	67.4 ± 0.7	-	-	-	-
Consortium (MLT, w/a)	97.7 ± 1.1	-	-	-	-
Consortium (sDWW, a)	65.3 ± 2.2	-	-	18,529 ± 3890	-
Consortium (sDWW, w/a)	36.8 ± 1.4	-	-	-	-
Consortium (sDWW, w/a, B.I.)	105.2 ± 3.3	1.7 ± 0.05	7.8 ± 0.8	1035 ± 257	5430 ±260
Chlam. mono. (sDWW, a)	-	-	-	318 ± 73	-
Chlamy. mono. (sDWW, w/a, B.I.)	9.4 ± 1.1	0.1 ± 0.04	1.0 ± 0.1	333 ± 35	11,120 ±236
M. forte mono. (sDWW, a)	-	-	-	64,559 ± 1530	-
M. forte mono. (sDWW, w/a, B.I.)	-	0.7 ± 0.15	1.0 ± 1.0	9229 ± 152	12,687 ±218
Not inoculated (sDWW, w/a, B.I.)	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.2 ± 0.1	-	-

markedly improved in non-agitated cultures ($105 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$), resembling MLT cultures (Table 2). A series of experiments using higher concentrations of WM (including undiluted WM) confirmed that non-agitated condition combined with bottom illumination benefited *Chlamydomonas* growth (Supplemental Fig. S2). These findings suggest that microaerobic conditions favor *Chlamydomonas* growth in this consortium.

3.2.3. Bioremediation capacity and CO₂ emissions

Biorremediation capacity was evaluated through COD measurements in cocultures and the respective monocultures incubated under non-agitated conditions and bottom illumination at 80 PPFD. The results confirmed a significant efficient reduction of oxidizable organic matter in the cocultures with a 55 % decrease in COD, while no significant COD reduction was observed in the monocultures (Table 2). Intriguingly, no COD reduction was observed in bacterial monocultures. This may result from the accumulation of intermediate metabolites and the incomplete oxidation of organic matter under microaerobic conditions that continue to contribute to COD.

Notably, the initial COD of sDWW ($12,077 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) far exceeded the typical range reported for most DWW (Table 1). It is also important to note that the cocultures were able to grow even in 1:5 WM-MM dilutions, which had a COD as high as $24,000 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ (Fig. 1). Excessive COD is often reported as a drawback for algal cultivation in DWW (Gupta et al., 2019; Kothari et al., 2013, 2012; Lu et al., 2016; Ma et al., 2023; Nayana et al., 2024), leading many studies to employ diluted or low-COD DWWs (Table 1) (Huo et al., 2012; Kothari et al., 2013, 2012; Kumar et al., 2023; Lu et al., 2016; Nayana et al., 2024). However, diluting DWW is neither sustainable nor practical strategy for large-scale treatment facilities processing raw effluents with high organic loads. Nonetheless, previous studies have successfully reported the growth of several microalgae species in DWW with high COD values ($4400\text{--}10,300 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) (Barsanti et al., 2021; Kothari et al., 2013; Lu et al., 2016; Modenes et al., 2024; Salah et al., 2023; Sanchez-Zurano et al., 2024)

CO₂ emissions were also measured in both agitated cultures with top illumination and non-agitated cultures illuminated from below, all incubated at 80 PPFD (Table 2). As expected, algal monocultures fixed CO₂ rather than releasing it, while both cocultures and bacterial monocultures released CO₂. Comparatively, CO₂ emissions were considerably lower in the consortium than in *M. forte* monocultures under all conditions, with reductions of 71.3 % and 88.8 % under agitated and non-agitated conditions, respectively. These lower CO₂ emissions in cocultures compared to bacterial monocultures may represent an added advantage of algae-bacteria systems over purely bacterial treatments for wastewater remediation. Notably, net CO₂ emissions were significantly lower under non-agitation conditions compared to agitation, for both cocultures and bacterial monocultures, with reductions of approximately 18-fold and 7-fold, respectively. These data likely reflect a severe decrease in bacterial respiration under microaerobiosis.

3.2.4. Effect of light intensity on biomass yield

The effect of different light intensities (50, 120, and 500 PPFD) on consortium growth (measured as chlorophyll concentration and dry-weight biomass) was assessed in cultures incubated under continuous agitation (Fig. 2). At 120 PPFD, chlorophyll concentration was highest ($104 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$ after 6 days), outperforming both 50 PPFD ($67 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$) and the markedly lower values observed at 500 PPFD ($27 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$) (Fig. 2A). Although light intensity may influence chlorophyll accumulation, it is reasonable to say that optimal algae growth occurred at 120 PPFD after 6 days. Eventually, all cultures reached a similar chlorophyll concentrations after 13 days ($87\text{--}107 \mu\text{g chlorophyll} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$), probably because as the number of cells increased, the self-shading mitigated the effect of the light. Dry-weight biomass after 8 days perfectly correlated with chlorophyll concentrations, with the highest yield observed at 120 PPFD ($11.27 \text{ g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$; $1.25 \text{ g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1} \cdot \text{d}^{-1}$), confirming optimal algal growth under this condition. In contrast, both low (50 PPFD) and excessive (500 PPFD) light intensities were detrimental to biomass accumulation (6.7 and $5.2 \text{ g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$, respectively) (Fig. 2B). Dry-weight biomass was also measured in non-agitated cultures illuminated from below at 80 PPFD, yielding $7.8 \text{ gr} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ after 7 days (Table 2), in line with the previous observed effect of light intensity.

Fig. 2. Effect of light on *Chlamydomonas-M. forte* cultures incubated in sDWW. A) Total chlorophyll concentration of the consortium cultivated in sDWW under 50, 120, and 500 PPFD. B) Dry cell weigh biomass from the cocultures incubated at different light intensities after 8 days. Cells were cultivated under continuous top illumination and agitation. Data represent the means of at least three biological replicates, and Standard Error of the Mean (SEM) values are indicated. SEM bars may not be visible in the current graphic scales.

Noteworthy, the consortium incubated in sDWW exhibited high chlorophyll concentration (up to $105 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$) and substantial dry biomass ($7.8\text{--}11.3 \text{ g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) (Fig. 2 and Table 2). Previous studies on microalgal cultivation in DWW have reported a wide range of biomass yields (from 0.175 to $11.6 \text{ g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$), with no clear correlation to the initial COD values. The average yield is around $3 \text{ g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$, and many studies reporting values below $1 \text{ g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ (Table 1). Most of these previous reports have used whey or whey-derived WW (Table 1). In contrast, the *Chlamydomonas-M. forte* consortium achieved significantly higher biomass (up to $11.3 \text{ g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$; $1.25 \text{ g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1} \cdot \text{d}^{-1}$) than most previous studies, using sDWW with a COD of $12,077 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$. This value is well above the COD values typically used for microalga cultivation in DWW, which range from 131 to $10,300 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ and average around $2,000 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ (Table 1). Only the cultivation of *Poterioochromonas malhamensis* yielded a biomass ($11.6 \text{ g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$; $0.9 \text{ g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1} \cdot \text{d}^{-1}$) comparable to that achieved by the *Chlamydomonas-M. forte* consortium, using DWW with a COD of $10,300 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ (Módenes et al., 2024) (Table 1). However, in the case of *P. malhamensis*, the components of the rich synthetic medium BG-11 were diluted in the DWW, and 5 % CO_2 was also supplied. In contrast, the *Chlamydomonas-M. forte* consortium required only trace elements. Overall, the *Chlamydomonas-M. forte* consortium demonstrated a strong potential to produce substantial biomass ($11.3 \text{ g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) when cultivated in highly polluted DWW (COD of $12000 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$), with minimal supplementation (trace elements).

Fig. 3. Bioremediation profile of the *Chlamydomonas-M. forte* consortium. A) Lactose, B) Acetic acid, C) Lactic acid, D) Total protein, and E) Ammonium concentrations in *Chlamydomonas-M. forte* cocultures and their respective monocultures. sDWW not inoculated was included as a control. All cultures were incubated in sDWW without agitation and continuous bottom illumination (80 PPFd). Data represent the means of at least three biological replicates, and Standard Error of the Mean (SEM) values are indicated. SEM bars may not be visible in the current graphic scales.

3.3. Functional relationships within the *Chlamydomonas*–*Microbacterium forte* consortium in sDWW

All the results described above indicate that *Chlamydomonas* growth in sDWW is supported by metabolic byproducts generated by *M. forte*. Furthermore, $^{SCS}OD_{600}$ values for *M. forte* were 2.4 times higher in cocultures than in monocultures incubated in sDWW under non-agitation and bottom illumination conditions (Table 2 and Supplemental Fig. S3), indicating enhanced bacterial growth in the presence of the alga. Previous studies showed that the *Chlamydomonas*–*M. forte* consortium establishes a mutualistic relationship when cocultured in media containing mannitol and yeast extract, leading to enhanced growth of both microorganisms (Fakhimi et al., 2024). In this interaction, the bacterium supplies ammonium and acetic acid to the alga, while *M. forte* benefits from thiamine, biotin, and reduced S compounds provided by *Chlamydomonas*. It is therefore likely that a similar mutualistic exchange occurs in sDWW, leading to a biomass yield 389 % greater than the sum of the individual monocultures (Table 2).

To better understand the interactions within the consortium in sDWW, key metabolites presented in the media broth (proteins, ammonium, lactose, acetic acid and lactic acid) were analyzed in non-agitated cultures illuminated from below (80 PPFD), and compared with those in the respective monocultures (Fig. 3). The initial concentrations of ammonium and protein in the sDWW were 2.6 mM (46.8 mg·L⁻¹) and 2.12 mg·mL⁻¹, respectively (Fig. 3D and E), values consistent with those previously documented for DWW (Lu et al., 2016; Ma et al., 2023; Slavov, 2017). No acetic acid or lactic acid was detected in the sDWW (Fig. 3B and C). As expected, *M. forte* was solely responsible for lactose uptake, as *Chlamydomonas* only efficiently assimilates acetic acid as an organic C source (Harris, 2009). Lactose uptake was more efficient in the consortium than in the bacterial monocultures, decreasing from 13.8 mM to 3.8 mM after 9 days (49.6 % more efficient than in *M. forte* monocultures) (Fig. 3A). Similarly, acetic acid accumulation was more pronounced in the consortium, reaching 1.66 mM after 9 days (Fig. 3B), likely reflecting enhanced bacterial lactose metabolism. Curiously, lactic acid excretion was only detected in *M. forte* monocultures (up to 3.9 mM after 9 days) (Fig. 3C). No significant pH change was observed in the consortium (from 7 to 6.7 after 7 days). Additional experiments using higher concentrations of WM, including undiluted WM, revealed that lactose uptake was enhanced under agitated conditions (Supplemental Fig. S2). Overall, acetic acid excretion correlated proportionally with lactose uptake, particularly in the absence of *Chlamydomonas* growth, as no acetate was consumed by the alga. In media with high lactose concentrations (e.g. undiluted WM), the elevated amounts of acetic acid excreted by the bacterium (up to 135 mM) were likely toxic to the alga and impaired its growth (Supplemental Fig. S2).

On the other hand, *M. forte* showed marked proteolytic activity, being faster in the consortium (Fig. 3D), while in monocultures, this activity led to ammonium accumulation in the medium (from 2.6 to 4.9 mM). In contrast, no ammonium accumulation was observed in the consortium; rather, ammonium uptake occurred (Fig. 3E). It is likely that the ammonium released through bacterial proteolysis was readily assimilated by the alga, preventing its accumulation in the medium. As previously noted, ammonium scarcity in DWW can limit factor algal growth, particularly in axenic algal monocultures (Lu et al., 2016). However, N is not a limiting nutrient when using *Chlamydomonas*–*M. forte* cultures in sDWW (Fig. 1).

As commented before, cocultures grown in sDWW (and in WM-MM) exhibited delayed algae growth compared to TAP, most likely due to the initial low availability of acetic acid (Fig. 1). However, chlorophyll concentration in the consortium was substantially higher in sDWW (55.3–105.2 µg · mL⁻¹; Figs. 1, 2, and Table 2) and in MLT (67.4–97.7 µg · mL⁻¹; Table 2) than in TAP (37.2 µg · mL⁻¹; Supplemental Fig. S1), despite TAP containing higher initial concentrations of ammonium (8 mM) and acetic acid (17.5 mM) than sDWW (2.6 mM ammonium and no acetic acid). It is reasonable to assume that in media containing lactose and peptides (sDWW and MLT), the gradual and sustained release of ammonium and acetic acid by the bacteria supports higher and prolonged mixotrophic algal growth than that observed in TAP.

The use of organic N sources (e.g., yeast extract or tryptone) has been shown to enhance algae biomass production in various microalgae species (Gu et al., 2015; Kim et al., 2016), including *Chlamydomonas*–*M. forte* cocultures (Fakhimi et al., 2024). Moreover, non-axenic algal cultures often grow better on raw DWW than in synthetic mixotrophic media (Hena et al., 2015; Kothari et al., 2013; Ma et al., 2023; Módenes et al., 2024). Overall, these observations suggest that the endogenous bacterial communities in DWW provide ammonium, assimilable organic C, and likely also assimilable P and S to the alga, ultimately making DWW an ideal medium for microalgae cultivation.

Identifying compatible algal-bacterial pairs remains a major challenge limiting the biotechnological use of cocultures. The type of interaction established between bacteria present in sDWW and different algal species (commensalism, mutualism, parasitism, neutralism, competition, or predation) can greatly impact algae performance. Furthermore, excessive bacterial proliferation often leads to significant pH fluctuations or nutrient depletion, ultimately hindering algal growth. In the *Chlamydomonas*–*M. forte* consortium, bacterial overgrowth is naturally constrained, as *M. forte* requires vitamins (biotin and thiamine) and reduced S compounds supplied by the algae (Fakhimi et al., 2024). Nonetheless, the potential interactions between algae and bacteria in DWW remain poorly understood, and very few studies have explored this aspect. Módenes et al. (2024) studied how the inoculation of *P. malhamensis* affects the endogenous bacterial community of DWW. Hena et al. (2015b) analyzed algal community survival in unsterilized DWW, while Kumar et al. (2023) described enhanced growth of *S. abundans* when cocultured with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* in unsterilized raw DWW. Similarly, Roy (2023) described improved growth of *C. vulgaris* in DWW when cocultivated with bacterial sludge. However, none of these reports fully addressed the influence of endogenous microbial populations on algal performance or the underlying metabolic interactions. Identifying stable mutualistic consortia, such as *Chlamydomonas*–*M. forte*, could greatly improve the reliability and scalability of algal cultivation in DWW.

3.4. Growth of *Chlamydomonas* in consortium with *M. forte* in raw DWW

The growth of the *Chlamydomonas*–*M. forte* consortium was assayed in non-sterilized raw DWW supplemented with trace elements.

Chlamydomonas monocultures were also included to assess whether the alga could grow in non-sterilized raw DWW without *M. forte*. Both cocultures and *Chlamydomonas* monocultures grew similarly at 80 PPFD (Fig. 4A), reaching chlorophyll levels ($58\text{--}65\ \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) comparable to those obtained in sDWW (Fig. 1). Moreover, COD was similarly reduced in both cocultures and *Chlamydomonas* monocultures (from initial 7346 to $300\text{--}345\ \text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), representing a $> 95\%$ decrease (Fig. 4B). The initial pH of raw DWW (6.5) moderately increased to 7.4 in both consortium and algal monocultures after 7 days.

These results indicate that *Chlamydomonas* does not strictly require *M. forte* to grow in raw DWW, as other native bacteria can also support its mixotrophic growth. Nevertheless, unlike the *Chlamydomonas*-*M. forte* cocultures, results from *Chlamydomonas* monocultures were only moderately reproducible across different raw DWW batches, exhibiting considerable variation in algal growth (data not shown). Variability in composition and native bacterial populations among DWW batches may impact reproducibility. Therefore, the use of previously optimized consortia, such as *Chlamydomonas*-*M. forte*, may offer advantages in ensuring process reproducibility and stability in DWWT.

Numerous studies have reported microalgal growth in unsterilized raw DWW (Table 1). However, little is known about which specific microalgae species can grow on their own in DWW, or whether they require the assistance of naturally occurring bacteria present in DWW. Several studies have examined the growth of various microalgae species in sterilized DWW (Beevi and Sukumaran, 2014; Hena et al., 2015; Huo et al., 2012; Lu et al., 2016; Qin et al., 2014). However, in most cases, DWWs were sterilized at 121°C (a process that can induce caramelization, Maillard reactions, and breakdown of organic molecules), and/or supplemented with nutrients (acetic acid, glycerol, ammonium) (Table 1). In both cases, the nutrient composition of the DWW is altered, making it difficult to assess whether these microalgae could grow in untreated DWW on their own.

3.5. BioH₂ production in sDWW

Previously, a multispecies consortium comprising *Chlamydomonas*, *M. forte*, *Stenotrophomonas goyi* and *Bacillus cereus* produced $\sim 160\ \text{mL}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ of H₂ in a synthetic medium containing yeast extract and mannitol, using an initial concentration of $10\ \mu\text{g}\ \text{chlorophyll}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ and incubated under 50 PPFD for 25 days (Fakhimi et al., 2024). This H₂ production was among the highest values reported for *Chlamydomonas*-bacteria cocultures (Fakhimi et al., 2020). Interestingly, H₂ production was concomitant with *Chlamydomonas* growth (up to $59\ \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ of chlorophyll), which is uncommon, as H₂ production conditions usually hinder algal growth. H₂ production was exclusively attributed to the alga, with no bacterial contribution. However, *M. forte* was key in promoting algal H₂ production through the secretion of acetic acid (Fakhimi et al., 2024), a metabolite that triggers H₂ production in *Chlamydomonas* (Jurado-Oller et al., 2015). Nonetheless, when using *Chlamydomonas*-*M. forte* cocultures under the same experimental conditions, H₂ production dropped to $\sim 70\ \text{mL}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, and algal growth was not observed (Fakhimi et al., 2024).

The capacity of the *Chlamydomonas*-*M. forte* consortium to produce H₂ in sDWW was first evaluated under the same experimental conditions previously reported by Fakhimi et al. (2024), including a light intensity of 50 PPFD (Fig. 5). Cocultures produced up to $185.8\ \text{mL}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ of H₂ after 14 days. Similar levels were obtained in 1:2 WM-H₂O dilutions ($162.5\ \text{mL}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) (Fig. 5A). As expected, no H₂ production was detected in the respective monocultures (Fig. 5A). Given the high opacity of sDWW, different light intensities were employed to assess whether H₂ production could be enhanced (50, 120 and 500 PPFD) (Fig. 5B). No significant differences in H₂ production were found. However, increasing light intensity had a positive effect on algal growth, with chlorophyll concentrations reaching $61\ \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ at 500 PPFD (Figs. 5C and 5D).

Fig. 4. Chlorophyll concentration (A) and COD (B) of *Chlamydomonas*-*M. forte* cocultures and *Chlamydomonas* monocultures incubated in raw DWW. Cultures were incubated in raw DWW supplemented with trace elements under continuous top illumination (80 PPFD) and agitation. COD was measured after 7 days. The algal growth in the consortium was measured as total chlorophyll. Data represent the means of at least three biological replicates, and Standard Error of the Mean (SEM) values are indicated. SEM bars may not be visible in the current graphic scales.

Fig. 5. Accumulative H₂ production of *Chlamydomonas-M. forte* consortium incubated in sDWW. A) H₂ production in sDWW (solid lines) and 1:2 WM-H₂O dilution (dotted lines) at 50 PPFD. B) H₂ production in sDWW under different top illuminations (50, 120 and 500 PPFD) and agitation (200 rpm). C) Chlorophyll concentration and D) actual photographs of the *Chlamydomonas-M. forte* cocultures in sDWW under different illuminations. Data represent the means of at least three biological replicates, and Standard Error of the Mean (SEM) values are indicated. SEM bars may not be visible in the current graphic scales.

Overall, the results obtained with the *Chlamydomonas-M. forte* consortium cultivated in sDWW significantly improved both H₂ production and algal viability compared to previous outcomes using yeast extract and mannitol (~70 mL · L⁻¹ of H₂ and no algal growth) (Fakhimi et al., 2024). Moreover, these results resembled those obtained with the multispecies consortium (160 mL · L⁻¹ of H₂ and 59 μg · mL⁻¹ of chlorophyll) (Fakhimi et al., 2024), while achieving faster H₂ production (14 days vs. 25 days) and reducing the microbial complexity from three bacterial species to just one. Hence, sDWW appears to be more favorable for H₂ production by the *Chlamydomonas-M. forte* consortium than the previous assayed media.

H₂ production was also tested in real permeate samples, a type of DWW obtained after filtration of the milk. In permeate, the consortium produced up to 47.5 mL H₂ · L⁻¹ after 11 days, although without substantial algal growth (Supplemental Fig. S4). The low protein content of the permeate likely limited algal growth due to N deficiency.

Overall, these results highlight the biotechnological potential of DWW for the simultaneous production of H₂ and algal biomass using the *Chlamydomonas-M. forte* consortium. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report demonstrating the feasibility of using DWW for microalgal-based bioH₂ production.

4. Conclusion

The *Chlamydomonas-M. forte* consortium produced a high biomass yield (11.27 g · L⁻¹) and substantial amounts of bioH₂ (up to 185.8 mL · L⁻¹) when cultivated in medium simulating DWW (sDWW, 1:10 WM dilution) with a very high COD (12,000 mg · L⁻¹), requiring only minimal nutrient supplementation (trace elements). Altogether, the ability of the *Chlamydomonas-M. forte* consortium to thrive in highly polluted DWW without the need for dilution and with minimal nutrient supplementation, while generating high biomass and bioH₂ yields, underscores its strong potential for wastewater valorization, contributing to water saving and lowering CO₂ emissions.

The mutualistic interaction with *M. forte* was essential to successfully fulfill these tasks, where axenic cultures failed. Although algal

growth was also observed in raw DWW supported by native bacterial communities, this approach may be less consistent and requires further investigation to ensure reproducibility and stability. The metabolic bacterial activities, including proteolysis and lactose fermentation, supply *Chlamydomonas* with essential N and C sources (ammonium and acetic acid), enabling its mixotrophic growth. In terms of biomass yield, the consortium performed best under microaerobic conditions without agitation and with moderate light intensity. This study highlights the relevance of elucidating algal-bacterial metabolic interactions for optimizing the valorization of DWW using microalgae.

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Research data

all raw research data are available at doi: 10.17632/vk6pgckhyx.1
E-supplementary data for this work can be found in e-version of this paper online.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Conceptualization, M.J.T., D.G.-B, and A.D.; Investigation, M.J.T., A.G.-O., J. D-L. and C.M-P; Results analysis and interpretation, M. J.T., A.G.-O., J. D-L. and C.M-P , D.G.-B., and A.D.; Supervision, A.D. and D.G.-B.; Project administration, A.G., A.D. and D.G.-B.; Resources, A.D., D.G.-B, and A.G; Funding acquisition, A.G., A.D., M.J.T, and D.G.-B.; Writing original draft, M.J.T., D.G.-B., and A. D.; Writing review & editing, M.J.T, A.D and D.G-B.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at doi:10.1016/j.eti.2025.104412.

Data availability

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Valorization of dairy wastewaters: large biomass and hydrogen production using an alga-bacterium consortium (Mendeley Data)

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